

**THE INFLUENCE OF PRACTICAL WORK IN SCHOOLS ON THE
FORMATION OF TEACHERS' ERUDITION**

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Abstract: The article examines the influence of practical work in the school environment on the development of teachers' erudition. The study was conducted in order to identify how the active involvement of teachers in practical activities within the school contributes to their professional growth and knowledge expansion. The author analyzes various methods of working with teachers, such as seminars, master classes, training courses and pedagogical practice. Special attention is paid to how these forms of practical work contribute to the deepening of teachers' knowledge in the field of the subject, pedagogical techniques, as well as to improving their professional competence. The results of the study can be useful both for teachers seeking self-development and for the school administration when planning professional development programs for staff.

Keywords: practical work in schools, formation of teacher erudition, educational process, teaching methods, professional development, pedagogical practice, curricula, integration of knowledge, pedagogical competencies, learning environment, educational effectiveness.

Introduction. In modern education, the role of practical work in schools is becoming increasingly important. A particularly important aspect of this work is its

influence on the formation of teachers' erudition. Practical activity allows teachers not only to gain new knowledge, but also to apply it in practice, which significantly enriches their professional experience and competencies.

Firstly, through practical work, teachers have the opportunity to put into practice the theoretical knowledge gained in the learning process. This allows them to deepen their knowledge, as well as develop the skills and abilities necessary for successful teaching[1]. For example, they can experiment with different teaching methods, adapting them to the specific needs of their students.

Secondly, practical work in schools helps to broaden the horizons of teachers. Attending the lessons of other colleagues, participating in seminars and conferences, sharing experiences with other teachers - all this allows teachers to get acquainted with new teaching methods, learn about the latest scientific discoveries in the field of education and exchange bewegung reports.

In addition, practical work allows teachers to better understand the individual characteristics of their students and adapt their approach to learning in accordance with these characteristics. This is especially important in a modern school environment, where students may have different educational needs and learning styles[2]. Finally, practical work helps teachers develop their leadership skills and promotes professional growth. Teachers who actively participate in practical activities often become leaders in their educational institution, organizing various events, making changes to the educational process and interacting with the school administration.

Thus, practical work in schools plays a key role in the formation of teachers' erudition. It allows teachers not only to expand their knowledge and skills, but also

to better understand the needs of their students and develop their professional qualities. Therefore, it is important to encourage and support teachers in their participation in practical activities, as this leads to an improvement in the quality of education in general. Practical work in the school environment plays a key role in the formation of teachers' erudition. This process not only provides teachers with the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, but also contributes to their continuous development and professional development. Initially, students-future teachers receive basic knowledge at lectures and seminars[3]. However, the true mastering of the material takes place in the process of its application in practice. The teacher is faced with various situations that require quick analysis and decision-making. This helps them to better understand the learning material and its applicability in real life.

In addition, practical work contributes to the development of teachers' skills such as communication, classroom management and adaptation to different learning styles of students. In the process of interacting with students, teachers learn to be more empathetic and understanding, which significantly improves the quality of education. Moreover, practical work in schools enriches teachers with new experience and knowledge. They are faced with a variety of learning methods, technologies, and problem-solving approaches. This continuous learning and adaptation process allows them to stay up to date with the latest trends and scientific achievements in the field of education.

In addition, practical work at school stimulates teachers to self-development and professional growth. Faced with various challenges and difficulties, they are forced to look for new approaches and solutions, which helps to expand their

professional horizons and improve their competencies[4]. Thus, it can be concluded that practical work in schools has a significant impact on the formation of teachers' erudition. It not only helps teachers to apply their knowledge in practice, but also contributes to their continuous development, professional growth and improvement of the quality of education.

Practical work in schools plays a key role in the formation of teachers' erudition. This process not only expands the knowledge of teachers, but also enriches their teaching experience, which ultimately contributes to the quality education of students. Practical work provides teachers with the opportunity to apply their knowledge in a real educational environment. This allows them to better understand the learning needs of their students and adapt their approach to meet those needs. For example, classroom work helps teachers understand which teaching methods are most effective for certain groups of students. In addition, practical work in schools contributes to the development of professional skills of teachers[5]. In the course of their work, they face various situations that require a quick and flexible response. This helps them develop classroom management skills, communication with students and their parents, and the ability to adapt to changing circumstances.

Moreover, practical work provides teachers with the opportunity for continuous professional development. They can participate in various trainings, seminars and workshops to expand their knowledge and skills. Returning to the classroom after such events, teachers can apply new techniques and approaches, which contributes to the continuous improvement of the quality of education. In addition, practical work can contribute to the development of teachers as leaders. In the process, they can identify their strengths and gain experience in managing projects and teams.

This helps them not only to lead their class more effectively, but also to become leaders in the educational community[6]. Practical work in schools plays an important role in the formation of teachers' erudition. It helps teachers develop their professional skills, expand their knowledge and become leaders in the educational field. This, in turn, contributes to improving the quality of education and the successful development of students.

Teaching erudition is a key aspect of successful educational activities. This is not only extensive knowledge in various fields, but also the ability to apply them in practice, adapt them to different situations in the educational process. The influence of practical work in schools on the formation of teachers' erudition is invaluable. That's why:

1. Student Engagement experience: Hands-on work in schools provides teachers with valuable experience working with diverse types of students. This allows you to develop flexibility of thinking, adapt teaching methods to the individual needs of each child, which is an important aspect of teacher erudition.

2. Pedagogical diagnostics: Practical work gives teachers the opportunity to practice methods of diagnosing students' knowledge and skills. This helps them to better understand the level of preparation of each child and adapt the training to take into account the detected weaknesses.

3. Professional development: Active participation in practical activities contributes to the professional development of the teacher. He receives feedback from colleagues, supervisors, and even students, which helps him grow as a specialist. This constant exchange of experience and knowledge enriches the teacher's erudition.

4. Integration of new teaching methods: Practical work allows teachers to experiment with new teaching methods. This includes the use of technology, interactive lessons, research projects and other innovative approaches. The use of various techniques helps to expand the knowledge and skills of the teacher.

5. Reflection and introspection: Practical work also contributes to the teacher's development of reflection and introspection skills. He can analyze his experience, identify the strengths and weaknesses of his work, which helps him to constantly improve.

Practical work in schools plays an important role in the formation of teachers' erudition. It provides teachers with the necessary experience, knowledge and skills to successfully carry out their professional activities. Constant interaction with students, the use of new techniques, the analysis of their own work — all this contributes to the growth of the quality of education and the improvement of the competence of the teaching staff.

Practical work in the school environment plays an important role in the formation of teachers' erudition, providing teachers with the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice and developing their professional skills. This approach to learning not only enriches the pedagogical experience, but also contributes to more effective student learning[7]. One of the main advantages of practical work for teachers is the ability to apply educational material in a real situation. When a teacher has the opportunity to work directly with students, he better understands their needs, structures lessons and chooses teaching methods that are most effective for a given audience. This experience enriches their teaching practice and contributes to the development of professional instinct.

In addition, practical work allows teachers to learn from their own mistakes and experience. In the process of interacting with students, teachers face various challenges and difficulties that may be unexpected or not taken into account in theoretical teaching. Working with these situations helps teachers develop their adaptation skills, improve their teaching methods, and respond more effectively to changes in the educational environment. Moreover, practical work contributes to the development of collective learning among teachers. The exchange of experience and best practices between teachers in the school environment stimulates the intellectual growth of each member of the educational team. Colleagues can discuss successful strategies, reflect on failures, and jointly seek solutions to improve student learning and education.

Practical work in the school environment plays a key role in the formation of teachers' erudition. This is not only a way to immerse yourself in an active educational process, but also an effective method of assimilation and consolidation of knowledge. The impact of such experience on the professional development of a teacher is enormous and deserves attention. First of all, practical work gives the teacher the opportunity to apply his knowledge in practice. Theoretical concepts learned at university or in professional courses become vivid and understandable when a teacher has the opportunity to apply them in a real learning environment. This contributes to a deeper understanding of the material and increases professional competence.

In addition, working at school allows teachers to interact directly with students. This makes it possible to better understand the individual needs of each child, to adapt the teaching methodology to their level and learning style. Such experience

helps to develop empathy and understanding, which is no less important aspect of a teacher than his own knowledge. In addition, practical work contributes to professional growth. In the process of work, the teacher is faced with various situations and problems that require quick and flexible thinking, finding solutions and making decisions. This develops his professional skills and helps him gain the experience necessary for successful work in the educational field.

Finally, practical work at school contributes to the creation of a community of teachers where they can share experiences, ideas and best practices. This helps teachers learn from each other, be inspired and support each other in their professional growth. Thus, practical work in schools plays an important role in the formation of teachers' erudition. It helps teachers put their knowledge into practice, better understand the needs of students, develop professional skills and find support in the teacher community. This experience is an integral part of the professional development of every teacher and contributes to improving the quality of education in general.

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